

LEVEL OF CULTURAL AWARENESS OF MUSLIM STUDENTS IN SAN JOSE NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL: BASIS FOR MADRASAH SCHOOL PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to determine the level of cultural awareness of Muslim students at San Jose National High School in Antipolo City. Purposive sampling was used by the researcher and used Mean Score for the level of cultural awareness with the four – point scaling as follows: (3.51 – 4.00) Very Much Aware, (2.51 – 3:5) Aware, (1.51 – 2.5) Quite Aware, and (1 – 1.5) Not Aware at All. Each of the forty-two (42) participants answered the survey questions. Experts validated the researcher-made assessment before administering it to the participants. Data were gathered from the participants using the survey assessment form made by the researchers, which is aligned to the Muslim Culture in terms of language, beliefs and practices. The results of the survey were as follow: The Muslim students' level of cultural awareness in terms of their language is 2.66 with a verbal interpretation of Aware; 2.59 mean score for their level of awareness in terms of their beliefs with a verbal interpretation of Aware and 2.66 mean score for their level of awareness in terms of their practices with a verbal interpretation of Aware. The study was limited to forty – two Muslim Students consisting of Grades 7 - 10 of San Jose National High School, school year 2022 - 2023. The level of awareness of the students on Muslim Culture was in the level of Aware. It only means that the teachers should strengthen their teaching approach inside the classroom through Madrasah Program for the students to increase their level of awareness of their Muslim Culture and eradicate the misconception about Muslim students. Different classroom activities must be done to

address the needs of the Muslim students such as teacher – student discussion, demonstration, role playing, reflective questioning and myths versus facts.

Keywords: *cultural awareness, Muslim, Madrasah Program*

INTRODUCTION

“Culture is a way of coping with the world by defining it in detail” is what Malcolm Bradbury said that gives emphasis on the importance of culture in one’s nation. According to DepEd Memorandum No. 41, Series of 2017, the Department of Education should offer a program that provides the following to the Muslim students in the Philippines: (1) provide Muslim learners with appropriate and relevant educational opportunities while recognizing their cultural context and unique purposes for participating in the Program offerings; and (2) integrate content and competencies which are relevant and of interest to Muslim learners. This policy seeks to harmonize existing DepEd issuances on Muslim education, with new provisions for more effective and efficient program development, implementation and evaluation. Moreover, this shall also serve as the basis for the development of the Manual of Operations for the Governance and Administration of the Madrasah Education Program (MEP).

Kafadar (2021) said that students mostly reported that cultural heritage was important since it was inherited from ancestors, it allows us to learn the past events, it reflects us, not to forget the old times, it is our culture, it is our history, for the perpetuity of our state, to learn about past lessons, and they stated that the cultural heritage should be preserved by state protection, followed by allowing it to live on, raising awareness, claiming it as a heritage, remembering, warning, and punishment, respectively.

Further, Yacoub (2023) revealed in his study that the Muslim students needed more support from their professors and departments to increase their visibility and empower them. Such support can come from means of critical pedagogy practices that challenge mainstream students’ misconceptions and biases about their Muslim peers.

Having said these facts, schools should think of ways on how to increase the awareness of the Muslim students of their culture and at the same time, eradicate the misconception of all the students about Muslim people.

Based on the summary of enrollment of Muslim students in San Jose National High School, school year 2022 - 2023, there are 13 Muslim students under Grade 7, 8 Muslim students under Grade 8, 11 Muslim students under Grade 9 and 10 Muslim students under Grade 10 with a total of 42 Muslim students.

This research study will be focusing on the level of awareness of the Muslim students on their culture and the ways that the school must be done to be able to help these students appreciate and love their culture that may contribute to build their self-

confidence and boost their self-esteem that they need for their over-all well-being and role in the society.

Teachers, therefore, need to apply teaching strategies that would help Muslim students engage in the classroom discussions without losing their own cultural awareness and gain the respect of their classmates at the same time.

It is in this light that this study is being proposed. It aims to fully find out the level of cultural awareness of the Muslim students in San Jose National High School, school year 2022 – 2023.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered after the study:

1. What is the level of cultural awareness of the Muslim students of San Jose National High School in terms of:
 - a. language;
 - b. beliefs; and
 - c. practices?
2. What specific school program will help the Muslim Students increase their level of awareness in terms of their Muslim culture?
3. What particular classroom activities can be done to preserve Muslim culture among Muslim students in terms of:
 - a. gaining the respect of non-Muslim classmates; and
 - b. eradicating misconceptions about Muslims?

METHODOLOGY

This study determined the level of cultural awareness of Muslim students at San Jose National High School. The respondents utilized in the conduct of the study were Grades 7 – 10 Muslim students at San Jose National High School during the school year 2022-2023. The data sources in this study were composed of 42 Muslim students from different grade levels in San Jose National High School. 13 Muslim students under Grade 7, 8 Muslim students under Grade 8, 11 Muslim students under Grade 9 and 10 Muslim students under Grade 10. The researcher used purposive sampling technique because the study was intended to Muslim students.

The researchers conducted a survey on the level of cultural awareness of the Muslim students in all grade levels with the following 4 – point scale: (3.51 – 4.00) Very Much Aware, (2.51 – 3:5) Aware, (1.51 – 2.5) Quite Aware, and (1 – 1.5) Not Aware at All. The survey form was validated of 3 experts in Araling Panlipunan, one (1) Head

Teacher and two (2) Master Teachers. The survey form was revised before it was given to the students. Another survey form was given to determine the different classroom activities which were appropriate to the needs of the Muslim Students. The researchers treated the gathered data using the mean score of the level of cultural awareness of the Muslim students using the 4 – point scale. For the other survey form, the data were presented based on the number of respondents who chose the specific classroom activities.

RESULTS

The following results are anchored on the research questions:

Research question No. 1. The level of cultural awareness of the Muslim students.

Table 1. Language

Indicator	Mean Score	Level of Awareness
1. Arabic is the most common language used by Muslims.	2.72	Aware
2. Quranic Arabic is the form of Arabic in which the Quran (the holy book of Islam) is written.	3.22	Aware
3. Quranic Arabic is also called classical Arabic.	2.61	Aware
4. Muslims use Arabic for prayers and other religious activities.	3.00	Aware
5. Arabic language unifies Muslims.	2.61	Aware
Average	2.66	Aware

Based on the table, the level of awareness of the Muslim students in terms of their language ranges from 2.61 to 3.22 with an interpretation of “Aware”.

Table 2. Beliefs

Indicators	Mean Score	Level of Awareness
1. Muslims have the creed of belief (shahada).	2.50	Quite Aware
2. According to the Qur'ān, God created two apparently parallel species of creatures, human beings and jinn, the one from clay and the other from fire.	2.50	Quite Aware
3. God alone, who reigns unchallenged in the heavens and the earth, is unlimited, independent, and self-sufficient.	2.44	Quite Aware
4. Prophethood is indivisible, and the Qur'ān requires recognition of all prophets as such without discrimination.	2.78	Aware
5. In Islamic doctrine, on the Last Day, when the world will come to an end, the dead will be resurrected, and a judgment will be pronounced on every person in accordance with his deeds.	2.72	Aware
Average	2.59	Aware

Based on the table, the level of awareness of the Muslim students in terms of their beliefs ranges from 2.44 (Quite Aware) to 2.78 that indicates the level of "Aware".

Table 3. Practices

Indicators	Mean Score	Level of Awareness
1. Muslims pray first standing and later kneeling or sitting on the ground, reciting prescribed prayers and phrases from the Quran as they bow and prostrate themselves in between.	2.72	Aware
2. Muslims practice giving to the poor (zakat).	2.83	Aware
3. Muslims practice daily prayer (salah).	2.78	Aware

4. Muslims practice fasting during Ramadan (sawm).	2.83	Aware
5. Muslims practice pilgrimage to Mecca (hajj).	2.11	Quite Aware
6. Traditional dress for Muslim men has typically covered at least the head and the area between the waist and the knees, while women's Islamic dress is to conceal the hair and the body from the ankles to the neck.	3.00	Aware
Average	2.66	Aware

Based on the table, Muslim students' awareness on their practices ranges from 2.11 (Quite Aware) to 3.00 (Aware).

Research question No. 2. Specific school program that will help the Muslim Students increase their level of awareness in terms of their Muslim culture.

Based on the survey form given to the students, San Jose National High School came up with a Madrasah Education Program (MEP) Enhancement that aims to strengthen the existing Madrasah Education Program to better integrate Islamic values and teachings with the national curriculum. The following activities will be included in the program: Islamic Cultural Awareness Programs that will promote understanding and respect for Islamic culture among students and teachers; Cultural Days: Organize school events to celebrate Islamic festivals like Ramadan and Eid, with educational activities about their significance; Workshops and Seminars: Conduct workshops on Islamic history, culture, and contributions to various fields such as science and art; Interfaith Dialogues: Facilitate interfaith dialogue sessions to foster mutual respect and understanding between Muslim and non-Muslim students; and Community Engagement and Service Projects that will encourage community service and engagement among Muslim students, reflecting Islamic values of charity and service.

Research question No. 3. Classroom activities that can be done to preserve Muslim culture among Muslim students

Gaining the respect of non-Muslim classmates

Table 4. Different Classroom Activities for Muslim Students to Gain the Respect of Non – Muslim Students

Classroom Activities	Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	Total
1. Questionnaires	1	0	0	1	2
2. Group Discussion	2	3	2	2	9
3. Student – Teacher Discussion	7	4	5	3	19
4. Reciting Verses from the Quran	0	0	1	1	2
5. Demonstration	3	1	3	3	10
6. Memorizing Individually	0	0	0	0	0
7. Memorizing in Groups	0	0	0	0	0
Total	13	8	11	10	42

Based on the table, only 2 students chose questionnaires; 19 students chose group discussion; 19 students chose student-teacher discussion; 2 students chose reciting verses from the Quran; 10 students chose demonstration; and no one chose memorizing verses from their bible.

Eradicating misconceptions about Muslims

Table 5. Different Classroom Activities for Muslim Students to Eradicate Misconception about Muslims

Classroom Activities	Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	Total
1. Think – Pair – Share	0	2	1	1	4
2. Reflective Questioning	5	2	3	2	12
3. Role Playing	2	2	2	2	8

4. Introduce Islamic Calendar	1	0	1	0	2
5. Islamic History Timeline	0	0	1	0	1
6. Methods of Islam	2	1	1	1	5
7. Video Lessons	1	0	1	1	3
8. Map of Muslim Countries	0	0	0	1	1
9. Myths vs Facts	2	1	1	2	6
Total	13	8	11	10	42

Based on the table, only 4 students picked think-pair-share; 12 students chose reflective questioning; 8 students chose role playing; 2 students chose to introduce Islamic calendar; only 1 student chose Islamic history timeline; 5 students chose methods of Islam; 3 students chose video lessons; 1 student chose map of Muslim countries, and 6 students chose Myths versus Facts activities.

DISCUSSION

Based on the first table, the level of awareness of the Muslim students in terms of their language for statement three has the lowest mean which means that the Muslim students are not familiar with Quranic Arabic as the language used in Quran. On the other hand, statement one got the highest mean that indicates that Muslim students are aware of their language which is Arabic. Thus, they know how to speak this language as Muslim students.

On table 2, the level of awareness of the Muslim students in terms of their beliefs got the highest mean in statement 4 which means that they are aware that prophet hood is indivisible, and they should be recognized equally and without discrimination. Muslim students know the value of equality among all the creations of Allah. Justness is part of their lives as Muslims. Statement three got the lowest mean under awareness level which means that some of the Muslim students do not know that God is the most powerful God of all based on their bible.

Based on table 3, Muslim students are aware of their traditional dress but they are not much aware about practicing pilgrimage to Mecca. Probably because they do not afford to go there because it is too expensive. It is one of the Five Pillars of Islam and a religious duty central to Muslim belief which every Muslim must make at least once in their lifetime. Unfortunately, not all Muslims can afford to go there.

Based on table 4, 45.23% of the Muslim students in San Jose National High School likes to have the learning about Muslim Culture by student – teacher discussion followed by lesson demonstration with 23.81% and the third most appropriate classroom activity is Group Discussion with 21.43% of the Muslim students. It only indicates that they are more comfortable learning the Muslim Culture with the guidance of their teacher and with their classmates' support and cooperation.

Schlein (2010) underlined existing opportunities for students and teachers to create an atmosphere of acceptance and understanding among cultural groups and for learning about the values, beliefs, and practices of individuals from diverse backgrounds in an increasingly interconnected global community. Thus, teaching the students about cultural differences can create atmosphere of acceptance among them. Acceptance of individual differences will develop respect among students inside the classroom.

Based on table 5, Reflective Questioning is the most appropriate classroom activity for the Muslim students of San Jose National High School with 28.57% of the total number of Muslim respondents followed by the Role Playing with 19.05%. The third most appropriate classroom activity that can eradicate the misconception about Muslim students is Myths versus Facts with 14.29% of the total number of Muslim students. It only shows that the opinion of non – Muslim students matter to the Muslim students. They need to know their thoughts about Muslims so that they can be able to correct the misconceptions right away. Further, reflective questioning will help the non – Muslim students to realize that Muslim students are not harmful. Role playing will also prove that Muslim culture can help them appreciate the richness of culture of the Philippines. It will also make them respectful and polite to their Muslim classmates and have a harmonious relationship inside the classroom.

The study of Pedersen (2009) described a nine-week anti-prejudice intervention targeting attitudes towards Australian Muslims at a Western Australian university in 2008 using data from 19 Psychology students. Quantitative results found a marginal increase in reported positive attitudes towards Australian Muslims, together with a significant reduction in the reporting of negative media-related beliefs. Therefore, a school program for Madrasah like conducting an intervention can help eradicate the misconceptions about Muslim students and increase their positive attitudes at the same time. Different classroom activities can be served as interventions depending on the needs of the learners.

Conclusions

The research study shows that the level of awareness of the students at San Jose National High School is at the average level which can be enhanced by implementing the Madrasah Education Program Enhancement.

According to Baer (2010), by learning to respect the rights and freedoms of others, as portrayed in the literature, readers will acquire a global perspective of awareness and tolerance for others. It is very important that the activities applied in the classroom would create harmonious relationships among students and build respect for Muslim and non-Muslim learners.

Saihu (2022) mentioned that multicultural learning model creates harmonious interaction. Furthermore, the integration of diversity understanding between Hindu and Islamic students aims to peaceful practices in the educational environment. Thus, the awareness of the students on their culture and the culture of others can build peaceful and safe ambiance inside the classroom. With these, the learners can freely express their ideas about the lessons without fear. Their learning capabilities will be fully maximized because they feel safe and secured inside the classroom. Therefore, learning the culture of Muslims can lead to a peaceful life, put the development of the country into perspective and acquire a global perspective of awareness and tolerance for others.

Additionally, Shadid (2006) stated that to understand fully the reasons for the drastic changes in Dutch immigration and integration policies and to be able to put current developments into perspective, it is important to survey the course of Muslim immigration in recent history and consider the awareness in Dutch society of these groups and their religion. This article traces the developments in public and political discourses on Islam in the Netherlands. Thus, it is essential to study the Muslim History and Culture to understand them and put an end to the misconceptions of others about them. With this, respect and awareness of their culture is built.

Morales (2020) said that it is important to highlight that Islam is a mosaic and not a monolith. Therefore, studying Muslim's culture in different perspectives can build a full understanding of their behaviour and way of socializing with other people. Through incorporating Muslim Education in the Education Curriculum is a big help for the Muslim

students to be understood and accepted and enhance their level of awareness of their culture at the same time.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were noted:

1. To address the educational needs of Muslim students at school, the school can implement a variety of programs and activities that are culturally sensitive and inclusive.
2. Provide specialized training for teachers on Islamic pedagogy and cultural sensitivity.
3. Develop and distribute textbooks and educational materials that align with both DepEd standards and Islamic teachings.
4. Develop Islamic cultural awareness programs that promote understanding and respect for Islamic culture among students and teachers.
5. Conduct more qualitative research to distinguish the needs from wants of the Muslim learners to specifically address their needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers prepared a letter to the Division Office asking permission to the conduct of the study. Then, a copy of the approved letter and a memorandum was sent to the school head. It was posted to the JHS teachers and chat group for information dissemination. The study participants were informed of the purpose of this endeavour and assured that the data collected was for research purposes only, in accordance with the Republic Act 10173 otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. They were informed that their anonymity and obtained information would be kept confidential, that their voluntary participation necessitated them to answer questionnaires within 5-10 minutes, but whenever they feel uncomfortable their participation can be withdrawn anytime, in which refusal or withdrawal involved no penalty or loss of benefits.

The researchers attested to the originality of this research study and have cited properly all the references used. They further commit that all deliverables and the final research study is of original content. They have used appropriate citations in referencing other works from various sources.

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